

LINEAR DIFFERENTIAL PURSUIT PROBLEM WITH MANY PLAYERS UNDER INTEGRAL AND GEOMETRIC RESTRICTIONS

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Abstract. We have considered a simple motion differential game of m pursuers with integral restriction and one evader with geometric restriction in \mathbb{R}^n . To solve a pursuit problem, the attainability domain of each pursuer is constructed. Sufficient condition of pursuit is obtained by intersection of the attainability domains. Lifeline game is solved for the advantage of the pursuers.

Keywords: Differential game, pursuer, evader, geometric restriction, integral restriction, attainability domain, lifeline.

Consider the differential game when the Pursuers X_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$, and the Evader Y having radius vectors x_i and y respectively move in \mathbb{R}^n . If their velocity vectors are u_i and v then the game will be described by the equations

$$X_i: \quad \dot{x}_i + ax_i = u_i, \quad x_i(0) = x_{i0}, \quad (1)$$

$$Y: \quad \dot{y} + ay = v, \quad y(0) = y_0, \quad (2)$$

where $x_i, y, u_i, v \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $n \geq 2$; x_{i0}, y_0 are the initial positions of the objects X_i and Y and it is assumed $x_{i0} \neq y_0$. Here the temporal variation of u_i must be a measurable function $u_i(\cdot): [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$, on which is imposed the constraint

$$\int_0^t |u_i(s)|^2 ds \leq \rho_{i0} \quad \text{for almost every } t \geq 0, \quad (3)$$

where $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$, and ρ_{i0} are the positive numbers. From the physical point of view, the right-hand of (3) corresponds to the given resource of the Pursuer X_i . We call the inequality (3) as integral restriction (briefly, I –constraint) and denote by U_i^I the class of admissible controls satisfying (3).

Similar, the temporal variation of v should be a measurable function $v(\cdot): [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ and on this function, we impose geometrical restriction (briefly, G –constraint)

$$|v(t)| \leq \beta \quad \text{for almost every } t \geq 0, \quad (4)$$

where β is a positive number which means the maximal velocity of the Evader. We denote by V_G the class of the Evader's admissible controls satisfying (4).

We are going to study mainly the game with phase restrictions for the Evader being given by a subset A of which is called the “Life-line” [1].

Definition 1. For each triple $(\rho_{i0}, u_i(\cdot))$, $u_i(\cdot) \in U_i^i$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$, the scalar function $\rho_i(t) = \rho_{i0} - \int_0^t |u_i(s)|^2 ds$, $\rho_i(0) = \rho_{i0}$, $t \geq 0$, is called the *residual resource of the Pursuer X_i* at the time t .

Let

$$z_i(t) = x_i(t) - y(t), \quad z_{i0} = x_{i0} - y_0, \quad \mu_{i0} = \rho_{i0}/|z_{i0}|.$$

Suppose that the pair (μ_{i0}, β) is a parametric state of the game (1)–(4) and denote it by p_i . We introduce the following nonempty connected set of such states p_i : $P_{IG}^i = \{p_i: \mu_{i0} \geq 4\beta, \beta > 0\}$.

Definition 2. The function

$$\mathbf{u}_i(v) = v - \lambda_i(v)\xi_{i0} \quad (5)$$

is called the *parallel pursuit strategy* (Π_{IG}^i -strategy) for the Pursuer X_i , where $\lambda_i(v) = \frac{\mu_{i0}}{2} + \langle v, \xi_{i0} \rangle + \sqrt{(\frac{\mu_{i0}}{2} + \langle v, \xi_{i0} \rangle)^2 - |v|^2}$, $\xi_{i0} = \frac{z_{i0}}{|z_{i0}|}$.

Consider the set

$$W_{IG}^i(t) = \{w: |w - x_i(t)|^2 = e^{-at} \Lambda_i(t, v(\cdot))(p_i(t)/\beta) |w - y(t)|, \\ 0 \leq t \leq t^*\},$$

where $t^* = \min\{t: |z_i(t)| = 0\}$ and w is a point where the Pursuers X_i should meet the Evader Y .

Theorem 1. Let $p_i \in P_{IG}^i$ be valid in the game (1)–(4). Then the relation $W_{IG}^i(t_2) \subset W_{IG}^i(t_1)$ is satisfied for any $t_1 < t_2$, $t_1, t_2 \in [0, t^*]$.

Proposition 1. If $p_i \in P_{IG}^i$, then inclusion $y(t) \in W_{IG}^i(0)$ is valid on $[0, t^*]$.

Theorem 2. If in the game (1)–(4), $p_i \in P_{IG}^i$ holds for some $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$, then $y(t) \in W_{IG}^i$ is met on the time interval $[0, T_{IG}]$, where $W_{IG} = \bigcap_{i=1}^m W_{IG}^i(0)$, $T_{IG} = d/\beta$, $d = \max\{|w_1 - w_2|: w_1, w_2 \in W_{IG}\}$.

Theorem 3. If $W_{IG} \cap A = \emptyset$, then the Pursuers X_i win on the time interval $[0, T_{IG}]$ in the “Life-line” game (1)–(4).

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